

REGIONAL ASPECTS OF OPTIMIZATION, PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AMONG THE ADULT POPULATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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The epidemiological aspects and main indicators of bronchial asthma (BA) incidence were studied in some regions (oblasts) of Uzbekistan. By analyzing the results on a representative sample of the adult population (768 people), innovations were proposed that contribute to the optimization of preventive services in real clinical practice with medical, economic and therapeutic effects.

As a result of the work, we came to the following conclusion:

1. In general, in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years there has been a decrease in the prevalence of respiratory diseases per 100,000 population (-2.5%). Also during the study period, a decrease in the prevalence of bronchial asthma (BA) was noted both in absolute numbers (-0.1%) and per 100,000 population (-3.0%). In addition, a decrease in the incidence of BA and respiratory diseases was noted both in absolute numbers (-16.3% and -1.9%, respectively) and per 100,000 population (-18.7 and 4.8%, respectively). An unfavorable situation in the prevalence of BA is typical for the city of Tashkent, Andijan, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Tashkent, Khorezm regions. An unfavorable situation with regard to the incidence of asthma is typical for the Andijan, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Fergana, Khorezm regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

2. On average, RF were observed in 11% of patients. The least favorable situation for RF among patients with bronchial asthma was in Tashkent and the Syrdarya region. The most favorable was in the Fergana region.

3. The main problem leading to irrational prescriptions are physician errors in interpreting the severity of the patient's condition. For example, according to GINA recommendations, patients diagnosed with mild intermittent bronchial asthma are prescribed only SABA, however, physicians in the RU who assessed the patient's condition as the mildest course of bronchial asthma prescribed GCS to such patients in 13% of cases, GCS in combination with LABA in 16%, and 16% of such patients used oral GCS daily. Among patients with mild persistent bronchial asthma, 68% did not receive GCS, but at the same time, 5% were prescribed LABA without GCS, and 3% of patients received oral GCS. With

moderate bronchial asthma, 25% of patients did not receive GCS, only 15 patients received combination therapy (both GCS and LABA), but along with this, 12 patients also took oral GCS. Among patients with severe BA, 8% of patients did not receive GCS, combination therapy accounted for only 21% of cases, and 54% received oral GCS. The analysis allowed us to conclude that among the studied patients with BA, only 46.2% of cases received pharmacotherapy that complied with GINA requirements.

4. The most effective way to optimize the treatment of bronchial asthma among the adult population of the regions of Uzbekistan is the compliance of prescribed drugs and doses with GINA requirements.

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